

Journal: <https://ifsmrc.org/index.php/aijrm>

UBAIDULLAKHAN'S ENTRY ONTO THE POLITICAL STAGE: HISTORICAL PROCESS AND POLITICAL PREPARATION

Abduvoidova Rukhshanakhan Akramjon qizi

Fergana State University, Faculty of History,
3rd year history student

Phone: 94-708-81-80, E-mail: rukshonaabduvoidova@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the process of Ubaydullah Khan's (1486–1539), an important figure in the history of Central Asia in the 16th century, entering the political scene. The study examines Ubaydullah Khan's genealogical position in the Shaybani dynasty, his formation in the political environment during his childhood and youth, the experience of state administration he gained through governing the Bukhara region, and his path to supreme power in 1533. Based on historical sources, the article emphasizes the role of military experience, religious and spiritual factors, and dynastic rivalry in Ubaydullah Khan's achievement of political maturity.

Keywords: Ubaydullah Khan, Shaybani dynasty, Movarunnahr, Bukhara governorate, 16th century political history, Safavids, Kochkunchi Khan, Abu Said Khan, Central Asia, state administration.

Ubaydullah Khan's emergence on the political scene was not an accidental process, but a logical consequence of complex historical and political processes within the Shaybanid dynasty. Although he was not a direct descendant of Shaybanid Khan, he was one of the most important representatives of the dynasty and belonged to the Shaybanid family by lineage. Historical sources mention Ubaydullah Khan as a close relative of Shaybanid Khan, a prince belonging to his lineage. Ubaydullah Khan was born around 1486-1487, and he was the son of Mahmud Sultan, one of the influential representatives of the Shaybanid dynasty. Mahmud Sultan was one of Shaybanid Khan's closest relatives and loyal commanders, and actively participated in the formation of the Shaybanid state. At the beginning of the 16th century, he was among the emirs who performed important military and political tasks in the territory of Transoxiana and ruled some provinces [1].

Ubaydullah Khan's childhood and youth (1490–1510) coincided with the period of the establishment of the Shaybanid state. It was during these years that the Timurid rule was ended under the leadership of Shaybanid Khan, and a new political system was formed in the territory of Transoxiana. From his youth, Ubaydullah Khan was brought up in an environment of these military campaigns and political struggles [2]. This situation directly influenced his worldview, political thinking, and future activities. Between 1500 and 1507, Shaybanid Khan seized Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, and other major centers, consolidating his power in Transoxiana. Although Ubaydullah Khan was still young at this time, he grew up in a military-political environment as a representative of the dynasty [3]. According to the tradition of the Shaybani dynasty, young princes were involved in state affairs from an early age, participated in military campaigns, and gained experience in governing certain territories. In 1510, Shaybani Khan was killed in a clash with the troops of the Safavid ruler Shah Ismail in the battle near Merv [4]. This event marked a sharp turning point in the history of the Shaybani state. Disunity increased within the state, and a struggle for power began between various princes and emirs. It was this

Journal: <https://ifsmrc.org/index.php/aijrm>

period (1510–1520) that became a school of political experience for Ubaydullah Khan. After the death of Shaybani Khan, political instability reigned in Transoxiana for a while. Many provinces began to act independently, while some regions fell under the influence of the Safavids [5]. During this period, Ubaydullah Khan, as a representative of the dynasty, was at the center of political processes, serving various rulers and participating in military campaigns. It was during these years that he began to manifest himself in the political arena.

Between 1511 and 1515, a struggle for power flared up within the Shaybanid state. After the death of Shaybanid Khan, first Kochkunchi Khan and then Suyunchkhodja Khan seized supreme power [6]. However, the central government weakened, and the number of princes and emirs acting independently in the provinces increased. It was during this period that Ubaydullah Khan began to appear more and more actively in political life. According to sources, Ubaydullah Khan initially carried out political and military activities in Bukhara and its environs. Between 1512 and 1516, he occupied an important position in the Bukhara region and tried to strengthen control over local emirs [7]. Bukhara at that time was one of the most important political and economic centers of Transoxiana, and control of this territory meant great prestige among the Shaybanids. It was here that Ubaydullah Khan began his activities that determined his future political fate. During the years 1516-1520, the Safavid threat remained in Transoxiana. The territories of Khorasan changed hands several times. Ubaydullah Khan participated in these processes as part of the Shaybanid troops and gained military experience. He began to be recognized not only as a representative of the dynasty, but also as a practical military leader. It was during these years that he was able to gather loyal commanders around him, which later became his political support. By the 1520s, relative stability had come to the Shaybanid state. Although the central government was relatively strengthened during the reign of Kochkunchi Khan (1510–1530), the regional governors were still inclined to act independently [8]. Ubaydullah Khan was formed during this period as a political figure who practically independently ruled the Bukhara region. Between 1521 and 1525, he consolidated his power in Bukhara and began to strengthen his economic and military base. Historical sources indicate that Ubaydullah Khan relied not only on military power in Bukhara, but also sought to establish close ties with scholars and religious circles. This policy helped him gain authority among various segments of the population. It was during this period that Ubaydullah Khan began to be recognized not only as a regional governor, but also as a significant political figure in the entire Shaybanid state [9].

In 1530, Kochkunchi Khan died. He was replaced by Abu Said Khan (1530–1533). However, the new khan's position was weak, and he could not fully control the influential princes and emirs among the Shaybanids. This situation created a political vacuum. It was this situation that created a great opportunity for Ubaydullah Khan. Between 1530 and 1533, the secret and open struggle for power in Transoxiana intensified. Ubaydullah Khan emerged as the most active and politically prepared figure in this process. Relying on his support in Bukhara, he managed to present himself as the most worthy representative of the Shaybanid dynasty. His military power, political experience, and connections with religious circles created the basis for his superiority over other rivals [10]. After the death of Abu Said Khan in 1533, the question of supreme power in the Shaybanid state remained open. At this time, Ubaydullah Khan, relying on his supporters, left Bukhara and headed for Samarkand. According to sources, the majority of the emirs supported Ubaydullah Khan's candidacy. As a result, in 1533 he was recognized as the Supreme Khan and became the supreme ruler of the Shaybanid state.

Ubaydullah Khan's entry into the political arena was the result of many years of preparation, military experience, provincial administration, and the ability to correctly assess the complex political situation. His early involvement in the formation of the Shaybanid state, his seizure of power in such an important center as Bukhara, and his political maturity in the 1520s and 1530s formed the natural historical

basis for his accession to the throne in 1533 [11]. Ubaydullah Khan's accession to the throne in 1533 was one of the most important political turning points in the history of the Shaybanid state. This event was not the result of a simple succession, but rather the result of many years of political preparation, provincial administration experience, and a correct assessment of the complex situation. After the death of Abu Said Khan, a political vacuum arose in Maverannahr, and competition for power intensified among the numerous princes of the Shaybanid dynasty. However, most of them did not have independent support or had not gained sufficient authority among the emirs.

Ubaydullah Khan, on the other hand, stood out from the rest with the political base he had formed in Bukhara since the 1520s, his loyal commanders, and his strong ties with religious circles. According to sources, in the spring of 1533, influential emirs around Bukhara and Samarkand agreed to support Ubaydullah Khan's candidacy. This indicates that he was perceived as the most suitable ruler among the Shaybanids. When Ubaydullah Khan entered Samarkand, he was proclaimed Supreme Khan at a meeting attended by scholars and emirs. This process served to strengthen his power not only politically, but also religiously and legally. Because at that time, the legitimacy of the ruler was directly related to the approval of scholars and recognition by religious institutions. Therefore, Ubaydullah Khan paid special attention to the support of religious circles during his accession ceremony [12].

With his coming to power, a new stage began in the Shaybanid state. In 1533–1534, Ubaydullah Khan sought first of all to ensure internal stability. It was necessary to strengthen control over the regional governors, who in previous years had become accustomed to acting independently. Ubaydullah Khan pursued a cautious policy in this regard: he left some emirs in their positions, and tied others to himself by bringing them closer to the center. In the period from 1534 to 1536, Ubaydullah Khan, along with maintaining political balance within the state, also paid attention to external threats. In conditions where the Safavid state remained under pressure from Khorasan, he reorganized the military forces and strengthened defensive measures in the border regions. It was during these years that Ubaydullah Khan began to demonstrate his independent political orientation as a ruler. One of the important aspects of his appearance on the political scene was the experience accumulated over many years of provincial administration. During his reign in Bukhara (approximately 1512–1533), he gained extensive experience in:

- regulating the financial and tax system,
 - organizing the military forces,
 - making peace with local emirs or subjugating them,
 - establishing balanced relations with religious circles.
- This experience transformed him from a simple representative of the dynasty into a real political leader. Ubaydullah Khan's appearance on the political scene was not a one-day or accidental event, but the logical result of almost forty years of his life. He grew up in the process of state building that began during the reign of Shaybani Khan, experienced a period of chaos after the death of Shaybani Khan, matured through provincial administration, and finally entered the stage of history in 1533 as the supreme ruler of the Shaybani state. It was this path - upbringing in a political environment from childhood, participation in military campaigns, gaining experience through provincial administration, and making the right decisions in difficult situations - that made Ubaydullah Khan one of the most important Shaybani rulers of the 16th century. In the following chapters, his political lines as a ruler, his path in domestic and foreign policy will be analyzed as a logical continuation of this formation process.

Conclusion

In general, the analysis of the topic “Ubaydullah Khan's emergence onto the political scene” shows that his entry into the historical arena was not an accidental process, but the result of the complex political situation, dynastic rivalry and personal preparation during the Shaybanid era.

Journal: <https://ifsmrc.org/index.php/aijrm>

The period of Ubaydullah Khan's formation coincided with an environment of intense struggles for power in the regions of Maverannahr and Khorasan, and the need to establish a centralized state was growing up. It was precisely these historical conditions that accelerated his entry into the political arena and made it necessary. Ubaydullah Khan grew up in an environment of rulers from a young age. Belonging to the Shaybanid dynasty allowed him to learn the traditions of state administration, the basics of military art and diplomacy early. He was distinguished not only by his lineage, but also by his personal qualities - determination, ability to understand the political situation, and religious and spiritual knowledge. These factors created the basis for the gathering of supporters around him and his active participation in political processes. Internal conflicts in the Shaybanid state played an important role in Ubaydullah Khan's appearance on the political scene. The struggle for power between the representatives of the dynasty, the weakening of the central government, and the desire of the regional governors for independence threatened to bring the state into disarray. In such conditions, Ubaydullah Khan appeared on the scene not only as a member of the dynasty, but also as a person capable of restoring order and stability. He initially strengthened his position through military campaigns and political alliances, gradually expanding his sphere of influence. In the early stages of his political career, the religious factor also played an important role. Ubaydullah Khan, having close ties with scholars and priests, sought to present himself as a ruler loyal to Islamic values. This increased his authority among the people and gave him an advantage over political opponents. As a result, he gained not only armed force, but also spiritual support. This was an important factor in the political environment of that time. Ubaydullah Khan's entry into the political arena was gradual. At first, he was prominent in regional activities, and later began to play a decisive role in national issues. This process enriched his political experience and helped him understand the responsibility of rulership. It was during this period that Ubaydullah Khan deeply felt the need for firmness and centralization in state administration. The measures taken during his later reign were the product of this early political experience.

References:

1. Zamonov. A. History of the Bukhara Khanate. - Tashkent. 2021. – B .127.
2. Akhmedov B.A. Istori Bukhari s drevneyshih vremen do nashih dnei. - Tashkent: Science, 1982. - S. 112–118.
3. Sagdullaev A.S. Mavlanov O'. History of state administration in Uzbekistan. - Tashkent. Academy. 2006. - B.156 .
4. Materialy po istorii kazakhskikh khanstv XV - XVIII centuries. - Alma-Ata, 1969. - S. 200-215.
5. <https://Islamicencyclopedia.org/tr/ubaydullah-han>
6. Erkayeva M. Bukhara Khanate during the reign of Ubaydullakhan I. // “PEDAGOGS” International Research Journal. Volume-83. – 2025. – P. 104–110.
7. Urinbaev A. Shaybani to the history due sources . - Tashkent : Science , 1965. - B. 43-50.
8. Mirzayev F. History of the Central Asian States. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2010. – P. 198-204.
9. Kholikova R. Political history of Central Asia in the 16th century. – Tashkent: Fan, 2015. – P. 75-82.
10. Dale SF The Muslim Empires of the Ottomans, Safavids, and Mughals. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010. – P. 78–85.
11. Erkayeva M. Bukhara Khanate during the reign of Ubaydullakhan I. // “PEDAGOGS” International Research Journal. Volume-83. – 2025. – P. 104–110.
12. Bacqué-Grammont JL Les Ottomans, les Safavides et leurs voisins. - Istanbul, 1987. - P. 112.